

Interconnected Lives in *The Overstory*: The Relationship Between Humans and Trees

Submitted by,

1. V. Preethi,

Assistant Professor,

Department of English,

Theni Kammavar Sangam College of Arts and Science,

Koduvilarpatti, Theni, Tamil Nadu, India.

2. J. Karthika, M.A,

Academician,

Theni.

Abstract:

The Overstory by Richard Powers' is a *Pulitzer Prize* winning novel that weaves together the lives of nine characters whose destinies become entwined with the natural world. All the characters of the novel show urgent action are required to protect the environment. Thus, this paper aims to establish a relationship between sustainability and trees which symbolize life. Trees play an important role for human survival. Because they are more tied to technology than to the natural world, people still do not care to preserve or protect forests. The nine different characters mingled with different kinds of trees. This paper conveys the idea to save nature and trees. The main theme is on the trees and their timeless beauty. The notion is to save nature.

Key Words:

Ecological, Environmental, Nature, Mulberry Tree, Banyan Tree,

Introduction:

The Overstory written by Richard Powers'. Richard Powers was born on June 18, 1957 in Evanston, Illinois. He is an American novelist whose works explore the effects of modern science and technology. Powers' was drawn to both highly experimental modernism with its conception of the novel as a self-justifying architectural form and the compelling tradition of narrative realism that trained the open eye on the world itself. His famous work, *The Overstory* (2018). It is Powers twelfth novel. The book tells the story of nine Americans

who, through their diverse life experiences with trees, come together to confront the issue of forest degradation. This work divided into four divisions, titled “roots”, “trunk”, “crown”, and “seeds”, reflect the stages of a tree’s life cycle. *The Overstory* focused on the Ecological concept and green plants energy in human life. A critical analysis of literature that looks at how humans interact with the environment is called Eco-Criticism.

The relationship between human and Nature:

Nicholas Hoel’s generation:

Jorgen Hoel and Vi Powys both got married. They moved to the new state of Iowa and started their farming life. But both were affected into the winter season. Both lived with nature which is why they were happy and independently led their lives. They kept working. Vi also became pregnant in the spring season. Jorgen found six chestnuts in his pocket and planted them. Jorgen Hoel’s first child died, and at the same time, one chestnut also died. After many years Jorgen and Vi had many more children. Years passed, and he kept fighting to keep his farm and save the chestnuts. One chestnut was killed in the winter time. Again, one Chestnut tree was accidentally killed by his oldest son John, who collected the leaves to use as play money. But he understood the impact of trees. The remaining three chestnuts grew.

Jorgen dreamed about the chestnuts. But one chestnut died. More than years passed and again one chestnut died. The reason was lightning strikes, it burned to the ground. But one chestnut remained alive. It grew strong and bloomed more than flowers. His youngest son worked in the Polk county Assessor’s office. His middle son became a banker in Ames. The eldest son John, stayed on the farm with his family. John bought a new tractor. Jorgen watched from the window side as the last Chestnut tree grew. He died soon. After John Hoel buried his father beneath the chestnut trees.

John bought new machines and he soon purchased a kodak No.2 Brownie camera. He took photos of everything. One day, John remembered the “zoopraxiscope” he bought for one of his daughters, and he came up with an idea. He decided to take photos of the chestnut tree growth. But his wife Calico teased her husband. On the east coast, a fungus kills chestnut tree arrived via the shipments of trees from Asia. Soon, it affected or spread across state lines and killing hundreds of thousands of trees.

John as 56 years old suddenly died. But even during his death, he took photos of the Chestnut tree. After John died, his two sons occupied the agricultural land. Frank decided to continue the photography ritual. In 1965, the camera broke but Frank Junior carried on. Many years passed and the Chestnuts tree also slowly grew while the Hoel family moved through generations. Finally, Hoel lands were occupied by factories. Frank also reached old age. His son Eric set up the camera and took the next picture of the chestnut. Eric's son Nicholas, was now 25 years old. Nick saw the photos and remembered his childhood. Nick remembered first telling his father that he wanted to go to art school. He was nervous, but his father quickly accepted the situation. Nick went to Chicago. But he continued to focus on drawing branches. He realized that the image came from the photos of the Hoel chestnut tree. Nick represented a generational conflict through his family's history of deforestation. Nicholas inherits a sense of responsibility towards nature, trying to redeem his family's past by replanting trees. His connection with nature is deeply personal, rooted in his family's land and legacy.

Douglas Pavlicek

Douglas Pavlicek's history is marred by tragedy. He was thrown from the jet upon enlisting in the Air Force. Luckily, he was discovered by a banyan tree, which ultimately saved his life. Thus, he shares a close relationship with the tree, and he feels obliged to repay this debt of gratitude. As he meanders across America, he comes across the clear-cutting of the national forest. On the other hand, it appears that the gas station cashier is indifferent to it. According to him, the national forest only exists for financial gain, with a particular party benefiting from it. This is an example of how to respect the forest. Furthermore, another datum demonstrates how Douglas' range increases in response to the sight of numerous trees that have been chopped down. The desire to fight someone is a result of his extreme rage.

Ray Brinkman and Dorothy

Ray Brinkman and Dorothy Cazaly, an intellectual property lawyer and a stenographer, start dating and performing in amateur theatre together. Ray proposes to Dorothy. They split up and then reconcile multiple times before deciding to tie the knot on a whim while on vacation in Rome. Every year on their anniversary, they arrange to plant something new in their yard.

Neelay Mehta

Next environmentalist, At the age of seven, Neelay Mehta the son of Indian immigrants, receives a functional early computer kit from his father Babul. Neelay develops an obsession with programming the computer after Babul and him work together to assemble it. A teacher once took his notebook, which included all of his computing work, and he cursed at her. Driven by humiliation, Neelay scales a tree only to tumble down, fracturing his back and become paralyzed from the waist down. Neelay uses a wheelchair to get through high school and is admitted to Stanford two years ahead of schedule despite being an exceptional coder. He quickly begins creating video games and offering them for free. He rolls his chair into the study area for his most recent game. He rolls his chair into Stanford's outdoor terrarium to investigate his latest game, and he's astounded by the diversity of trees that appear like aliens. He is given a vision of what needs to be done: make a game that immerses gamers in a whole new universe.

Patricia Westerford

Patricia Westerford is a biologist who conducts studies and discovers that trees can converse with one another. Her book *The Secret Forest*, which she authored on woods, was later revised. Views of many individuals toward nature, particularly trees. Her work symbolizes the concept of the Earth as a whole and asserts the equality of mankind and the natural world. The significance lies in its suggestion that people should treat nature with the same respect that they do themselves. Patricia included his viewpoint in her work to serve as a reminder to readers of the significance of nature's existence. She expresses his appreciation to a living creature that plays a crucial part in the ecosystem. She lists numerous items that people have been stealing from the tree for a long time.

Patricia finds that trees are an excellent social community through her studies on them. She describes in her journal how trees may talk to each other and provide care for one another. She then goes into great detail to explain how important trees are to all other living things on Earth, including humans, animals, microorganisms, and others. In fact, some species even benefit from dead trees. She describes how incredible. She writes in her journal that every part of the tree is beneficial, from life to its death. Patricia plays a significant role because she is an accomplished public speaker and scholar. She addresses the crowd, urging them to preserve the forest. Her speech straightforward yet essential. She highlighted the

benefits of trees that all people require. All life on earth could depend on trees for the maintenance of the ecosystem's equilibrium, clean water, and clear air. As a result, trees-exploitation need to end or at the very least be curtailed.

Olivia Vandergriff

Olivia Vandergriff is another character exhibiting environmentalist behaviour. She is a young lady who commits herself to opposing deforestation and becomes an environmentalist. It started one evening after she had finished her shower, and she returned to her bedroom with a body full of water. One of the wall sockets shocked her. Her heart pauses for a moment, and when she wakes up, she discovers that an enigmatic light creature visited her. She makes her way from her college to the California old-growth redwood forest in order to join a sizable group of activists fighting deforestation. She informs her father over the phone that she won't be able to complete her studies on time. She values trees more than herself and is prepared to take a break from college to assist in this voluntary work. She displays a true movement for the preservation of nature.

Conclusion

The Overstory focused on the human and trees relationship. The relationship of human society to the natural world is an ongoing tension in our society that drives the action of the novel. The main characters find themselves in constant conflict with the rest of the world concerning their relationships to the world concerning their relationships to the trees and Forests they come to love. But now the society people destroyed the nature. The nine Americans throughout life sacrifice their life to nature. Everyone learn from this novel the human help to nature means it is help to human life. So don't destroy the nature.

References

- Powers, Richard. *The Overstory*. Vintage, Penguin Random House, 2018. Print.
- <https://literariness.org/2016/11/27/ecocriticism/>
- <http://etheses.uin-malang.ac.id/34004/1/17320176.pdf>
- <https://rupkatha.com/V12/n5/rioc1s10n6.pdf>
- https://salsu.journals.ekb.eg/article_286373_e7e72cd7a12b4161525de4022acaccaf.pdf